

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: UNIMOS

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report – Poland

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of UNIMOS for the organisation and validation of the "Let's meet! Spotkajmy się!" event in Poland on March 11, 2023. This event is one of the four "Let's meet!" event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the "Let's meet!" tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the "Let's meet! Spotkajmy się!" event in Poland.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the "Let's meet!" guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the "Let's meet!" tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

"Let's meet! Spotkajmy się!" event in Poland was organized on 11th March 2023, at the European University of Social and Technical Sciences in the city of Radom located in the southern part of the Mazovia region and 100km from the capital Warsaw.

The concept selected was a **Producer event**. It was based on local products, accompanied by lectures from the producers and experts in the field of SFSC, healthy and nutritious diet, brand building and public health educational offer.

In order to implement the event, several preparative activities took place that consisted of:

1. In-depth analysis of deliverables related to needs of Polish stakeholders in terms of building SFSC
2. Consultations with Polish farmers about their availability
3. Analysis of potential venues and its logistic and technical possibilities
4. Selection of best date, venue, format and programme that would be attractive to participants
5. Preparation of materials and graphics to promote the event
6. Engagement, relationship building and promotional activities
7. Logistic organization and implementation of the event
8. Execution of the meeting and feedback gathering

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Presenter	Date & Time (local)
Date: 11 th March 2023			
Location: European University of Social and Technical Sciences (EUST) in Radom			
Activity #1	Welcome and opening session	Anna Bialik, UNIMOS Dariusz Stankiewicz, EUST Radom	11:00 – 11:40
Activity #2	Presentation of local apple orchard farm	Monika Bankiewicz, Gospodarstwo Sadownicze BANKIEWICZ	11:40 – 12:00
Activity #3	Brand building within SFSC	Anna Słowiecka, Noble Brand	12:00 – 12:30
Activity #4	Presentation and discussion on how to build SFSC in Poland and how to finance it using portfolio of UNIMOS projects, services and networks.	Anna Bialik, UNIMOS	12:30 – 13:00
Activity #5	Degustation of local products in form of food catering based on common competences.	Camelot Catering	13:00 – 13:30
Activity #6	Networking between participants	All participants	13:30 – 14:00
Activity #7	Closing session and evaluation	Anna Bialik UNIMOS	14:00

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The meeting was organized at the European University of Social and Technical Sciences (EUST). The university is located in the city of Radom and located 100km from the capital (Warsaw). The organization actively participates in the scientific, cultural, and economic life, both locally and internationally. It was chosen because of the alignment of its mission, values and educational offer with the concept of SFSC, as well as its openness to get engaged in initiatives that can have impact on their students and local communities. The venue was recommended by one of the farmers that is co-founder of AgroBioCluster coordinated by UNIMOS Foundation.

In order to ensure the possibility to organize the event, a formal letter was sent to high authorities who accepted to host the meeting at the university building. Representatives of the authorities, Dean of the Faculty of Social and Medical Sciences Dr. Iwona Pałgan and Mr. Dariusz Stankiewicz, took active part both in the preparation and the implementation of the event. A big classroom was put at disposal with all necessary technical equipment.

Figure 1: Venue setup

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

The event was organized by UNIMOS team in collaboration with personnel of the European University of Social and Technical Sciences (EUST) and in partnership with AgroBioCluster members that mostly are located in the Radom region.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	1 person day
Catering	3	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A
Speaker	1	Person introducing guests to the concept, products, producers and collecting feedback	External	1 person day
Organisation	2	Setting all details. Event promotion.	In-house	2 person days

2.4 Event material

The event was promoted on UNIMOS social media channels. Information was also distributed at the European University of Social and Technical Sciences (EUST) in Radom, where the event was organised.

Figure 2: Graphic for promotional use

Figure 3: Business card with Project's webpages

Figure 4: Invitation from UNIMOS LinkedIn Profile

U. UNIMOS Alliance
317 followers
2w • 🌐

Zapraszamy do Radomia!
Spotkajmy się! Polska edycja wydarzenia Let's Meet organizowanego w 12 krajach europejskich w ramach [AgroBridges Project 2021-2023](#)

Spotkajmy się na degustacji kulinarnej bazującej na produktach lokalnych i porozmawiajmy jak budować krótkie łańcuchy dostaw żywności (#SFSC).

Prelekcję poprowadzi [Anna Bialik](#), z towarzyszeniem [Monika Bankiewicz](#) i [Anna Słopecka](#).
A [#CamelotCatering](#) zapewni pyszne dania.

#localfood #Polish #fresh

See translation

Figure 5: Invitation from UNIMOS Facebook Profile

U. Unimos
10 marca o 22:26 · 🌐

Zapraszamy do Radomia!
Spotkajmy się! Polska edycja wydarzenia Let's Meet organizowanego w 12 krajach europejskich w ramach projektu [#AgroBridges](#).

Spotkajmy się na degustacji kulinarnej bazującej na produktach lokalnych i porozmawiajmy jak budować krótkie łańcuchy dostaw żywności (#SFSC).

Prelekcję poprowadzi [Anna Bialik](#), z towarzyszeniem [Monika Bankiewicz](#). A wspiera nas [Anna Słopecka](#) z [Agencja Kreatywna Noble Brand](#)

Pyszne przekąski zapewni [#CamelotCatering](#)

Bądźcie tam z nami!

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Different types of contributors and collaborators have been engaged in the organization of the event. As SFSC topic is becoming more and more popular in Poland, the event brought instant attention and attracted different stakeholders and partners from UNIMOS network who expressed their will to support its organization. The event was facilitated by UNIMOS team in collaboration with EUST's personnel and in partnership with AgroBioCluster members that are specializing in agri-food production, catering and restaurants and auxiliary services, such as branding and marketing. All organisational arrangements started 4 weeks before the event. After the final date and time were set, invitation was shared on social media, the event was created, and information was shared with the network. 1 week before the final menu was confirmed. Additionally, food catering arrangements were arranged in line with agroBRIDGES formal colour palette (orange and green) to transmit holistic and coherent project identity.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The engagement and promotional strategy to reach out businesses, farmers and other agri-food stakeholders included social media posts, emails and direct contacts. Special attention was put on students of EUST university in Radom who are studying public health and/or interested in healthy and fresh food. Approximately 1 week before the social media event was created on LinkedIn, Facebook, social media posts were shared, and invitations sent directly to UNIMOS networks and AgroBioCluster members.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

The event in Poland was divided into seven sessions. The first opening session included the welcome speech delivered by UNIMOS and the introduction of the European University of Social and Technical Sciences (EUST) delivered by the Dean and the Chancellor. Following, agroBRIDES project, its goals and activities were presented, together with developed resources and agroBRIDGES toolbox that is in process of validation.

The third session was dedicated to local farmer and owner of apple orchard Gospodarstwo Sadownicze MB Monika Bankiewicz. The company is specialized in the production of dessert apples and natural, cold-pressed apple juices. The owner shared the history of the orchard as a family business and commented on the whole production process needed to manufacture above mentioned products. Participants had also the opportunity to learn the story about the newest healthy product made from apples – apple vinegar. It was developed in collaboration with one of the top Polish research institutes and has supreme nutritional qualities beneficial for health.

The importance of the brand creation, communication and promotion was delivered by Anna Słopiecka – the owner of Noble Brand company that is a member of AgroBioCluster and has vast experience in uniting entrepreneurs around common economic and social initiatives.

Following, the presentation and discussion about building and financing SFSC in Poland and Radom region took place. To make it tangible, Anna Bialik – vice-president of UNIMOS Foundation – presented the organization's activities and project portfolio to support [international development](#) and [expansion](#). After the

presentations, participants were invited to taste apple juices with local food catering. It was designed to be based on local and fresh products made by local entrepreneurs and coordinated by Camelot Catering.

Figure 6: Examples of local food served during the event

Figure 7: UNIMOS' Vice President, Anna Bialik during the event

Figure 8: Food samples made with local products

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	4
Consumers	42
Academic teachers	4
Total	50

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event	23		28		0	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #2: Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	36	15	0	0	0	0
Question #3: Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	34	15	15	2	0	0
Question #4: Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	31	20	0	0	0	0
Question #5: Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	25	24	2	0	0	0
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	11	17	17	5	0	1

Pytanie nr 1: Czy przed tym wydarzeniem znałeś/aś koncepcję Krótkich Łańcuchów Dostaw Żywności?
51 odpowiedzi

Pytanie nr 4: Czy zorganizowane zajęcia okazały się pomocne w zrozumieniu wartości lokalnej żywności, lokalnych przepisów i ich różnych korzyści dla zdrowia, środowiska i społeczeństwa?
51 odpowiedzi

Pytanie nr 2: Czy to wydarzenie było dla Ciebie źródłem wiedzy o nowych/nieznanych rodzajach żywności produkowanej w Twoim regionie?
51 odpowiedzi

Pytanie nr 5: Czy znalazłeś/aś wystarczająco dużo informacji o tym, jak i gdzie znaleźć lokalne restauracje, lokale gastronomiczne oraz firmy hotelarskie, które poznałeś/aś?
51 odpowiedzi

Pytanie nr 3: Czy to wydarzenie było dla Ciebie pomocne w poznaniu lokalnych firm spożywczych, restauracji, ich metod i działań mających na celu zapoznanie Cię z lokalną żywnością?
51 odpowiedzi

Pytanie nr 6: Czy chciałbyś, aby w Twoim regionie zorganizowano kolejne podobne wydarzenie? Jak często?
51 odpowiedzi

4.1.2 Validation of "Let's meet!" guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The concept is very relevant and successful, because soon after the meeting, a new SFSC was created by one of the farmers who was the speaker at the event. The company started to deliver and sell apple juices directly to students who are attending university classes on bimonthly format basis (on weekends). Radom is located 30 min from the orchard, so it is both cost- and time-effective to organize own transportation on specific days to deliver products directly to consumers.

Question #2: Would you organize the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Taking into account the positive feedback, organization of similar activities in the future is seriously being considered. It could be organized in the same way, with more speakers from the UNIMOS network.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, guidelines were sufficient and allowed smooth organization of the event.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, guidelines were accurate and helpful to help plan effectively.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the instructions guidelines we were flexible, and the event was organized to meet needs of business, university, students, organizers and other stakeholders.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The event was organized at the premises of the EUST university and was oriented on engaging their students who attend classes on weekends. The event brought so much attention that more people were interested in joining the event and needed to bring additional chairs to the classroom.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Instructions were sufficient and very useful. It was possible to design, prepare and implement the event that was well received by participants. Simplification of the feedback forms to one pager documents would facilitate and speed up the preparation and collection of documents.

5. Conclusions

The “Let’s meet!” event in Poland was not only a great opportunity to promote SFSCs, but it also supported the development of one new sales channel just one month after the event was implemented. In the organization of the event and facilitation of SFSC, UNIMOS took into consideration all learning and resources developed within the agroBRIDGES project that served as a guidance. It was also combined with experiences exchanges from Irish Agropreneur Series launched in September 2022 where we had the opportunity to learn about Irish, Dutch and Lithuanian successful experiences of SFSC and shared them with Polish food producers. After the degustation of the premium juices, the participants of Let’s meet event in Poland were interested in buying it, so the company organized a direct delivery to address this need and meet their expectations. The organization of the event was a great learning experience and the success of building a real bridge between consumers and producers – that was rewarding and motivating to keep working on developing SFSC in Poland.